

Apical [u] (and other impractical articulations)

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Abstract

The human vocal tract allows compensatory articulation, maintaining phonetic target consistency even in abnormal conditions, such as fitted with bite blocks (Gay et al., 1981) or exposed to perturbed auditory (MacDonald et al., 2010; Mitsuya et al., 2011) and somatosensory feedback (Houde & Jordan, 1998; Katseff et al., 2012). While speakers can compensate for many circumstances, the resulting alternative articulatory configurations may carry a higher cost in terms of effort. As an example extraordinary, we explore the apical production of /u/, in which the tip of the tongue is curved back towards velum to create a constriction somewhat similar to that of a typical /u/. We conducted a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) single-subject case study at the Stockholm University Brain Imaging Center (SUBIC). The scanner was a Siemens Prisma 3 Tesla whole-body MRI. Data collection used the “FLASH” sequence - a spoiled gradient echo with a flip angle of 5 degrees, an echo time of 1.7 ms, and a repetition time of 4 ms. The field of view was 280(freq) x 278(phase) mm, with a resolution of 224(freq) x 156(phase) and a bandwidth = 500 Hz/px. The subject was a single adult male aged 28 at the time of recording. The speaker produced /u/ and “apical /u/” as sustained phonation, and as VCV and VCVCV sequences for /p l n t k/. Each form was uttered ten times as /u/, and subsequently ten times as “apical /u/”. In producing “apical /u/”, our speaker was able to maintain vowel quality and formant characteristics typical of /u/. Coarticulatory potential was highly variable, being mostly unaffected for /p/, but highly destructive to intelligibility for /n/ and /l/ - both of which typically involve the tongue tip or blade and are not straightforwardly compensated for by the dorsum. /t/ and /k/ were reasonably compensated for through movements of the dorsum and tongue root, mostly maintaining auditory equivalence.

References

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